

Chlorosulphonylation of the Methyl Ethers of Xylenols

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Methyl ethers of the six isomeric xylenols have been chlorosulphonylated and the position of the chlorosulphonyl group in each of the resulting sulphonyl chlorides has been established.

In the course of an investigation on the sulphur compounds derived from xylenols, we find that no study of the chlorosulphonylation of the methyl ethers of the various isomeric xylenols has been made. Such a study seems to be of interest because the resulting sulphonyl chlorides can be used to obtain the corresponding thiols, sulphides, sulphinic acids, sulphoxides, and sulphones easily.

The methyl ethers of the six isomeric xylenols (2,3-, 2,4-, 2,5-, 2,6-, 3,4-, and 3,5-dimethylanisole) furnished good yields of the sulphonyl chlorides on treatment with chlorosulphonic acid in chloroform medium. The sulphonyl chlorides were then converted into the corresponding sulphonamides since the latter could be obtained in a higher state of purity and analysed more conveniently. The relevant data on the sulphonyl chlorides and the sulphonamides are recorded in Table I.

In order to establish the position of the chlorosulphonyl group, the sulphonyl chlorides were subjected to the Friedel-Crafts reaction with benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Demethylation also occurred during the course of the reaction and the product in each case was a hydroxysulphone. 4-Hydroxy-2,3-dimethyl- (m.p. 191-92°), 4-hydroxy-2,5-dimethyl- (m.p. 162-63°), 4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethyl- (m.p. 235-36°), and 2-hydroxy-4,5-dimethyl-diphenyl sulphone (m.p. 150-51°) were obtained from the sulphonyl chlorides derived from 2,3-, 2,5-, 2,6- and 3,4-dimethylanisole, respectively. The above hydroxydiaryl sulphones were identified by comparison with samples synthesised unequivocally¹.

Though we expected to obtain 2-methoxy-3,5-dimethylbenzenesulphonyl chloride (I) from 2,4-dimethylanisole, the product actually isolated was 5-methoxy-2,4-dimethylbenzenesulphonyl chloride (II).

The sulphonyl chloride reacted with benzene with demethylation in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to provide 5-hydroxy-2,4-dimethyldiphenyl sulphone (m.p. 166-67°)*. It is therefore concluded that the position taken up by the $-\text{SO}_2\text{Cl}$ group is governed by the directive influence of the two nuclear methyl groups and not that of the methoxyl group².

The sulphonyl chloride derived from 3,5-dimethylanisole, when subjected to the Friedel-Crafts reaction with benzene, afforded a pasty product which could not be crystallised. So it was converted into the corresponding sodium sulphinate and methylated. The resulting compound was found to be 4-methoxy-2,6-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphone³.

TABLE I

Sulphonyl chlorides and sulphonamides derived from dimethylanisoles.

Anisole sulphonylated.	Benzenesulphonyl chloride obtained.	M.P. or B.P. of the sulphonyl chloride.	M.P. of the sulphonamide.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.	
				Found.	*Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
2,3-Dimethyl	4-Methoxy-2,3-dimethyl	76-77°	160-83°	50.32	50.21	6.39	6.09
2,4-Dimethyl	5-Methoxy-2,4-dimethyl	154-56°/12 mm	193-04°	50.51	50.21	6.20	6.09
2,5-Dimethyl	4-Methoxy-2,5-dimethyl	98-99°	214-15°	50.28	50.21	6.26	6.09
2,6-Dimethyl	4-Methoxy-3,5-dimethyl	136-38°/22 mm	108-10°	50.06	50.21	6.32	6.09
3,4-Dimethyl	2-Methoxy-4,5-dimethyl	113-14°	178-79°	50.53	50.21	6.10	6.09
3,5-Dimethyl	4-Methoxy-2,6-dimethyl	167-70°/16 mm	140-41°	50.46	50.21	6.10	6.09

*All the sulphonamides have the molecular formula $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{NS}$.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Procedure for Chlorosulphonylation.—A solution of the dimethylanisole (20 g.) in dry chloroform (100 ml) was kept stirred and treated slowly with chlorosulphonic acid (100 g.), the temperature being kept at 0 to 5°. After 1 hour, the reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous MgSO_4 . Evaporation of the solvent furnished the sulphonyl chloride.

Preparation of Sulphonamides.—A solution of the sulphonyl chloride in chloroform was treated with NH_4OH solution (conc.) and kept on a water bath for a few minutes. Evaporation of the solvent afforded the sulphonamide. It was recrystallised from dilute ethanol.

2. Kotlan and Wessely, *Monatsh.*, 1957, 88, 130.

3. Kloosterziel and Bosker, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1953, 72, 193.

Friedel-Crafts Reaction of the Sulphonyl Chlorides with Benzene.—To the sulphonyl chloride (4.8 g.), dissolved in dry benzene (80 ml), was added with stirring anhydrous aluminium chloride (9.2 g.). The mixture was heated to reflux on a water bath for 2 hours, cooled, and decomposed with ice and HCl. The benzene layer was separated, washed with water, and extracted with dilute alkali. Neutralisation with HCl gave the hydroxysulphone. The sulphones were recrystallised from ethanol.

4-Methoxy-2,6-dimethylphenyl Methyl Sulphone.—4-Methoxy-2,6-dimethylbenzenesulphonyl chloride was reduced to sulphinic acid with zinc dust and water. The sodium salt of the sulphinic acid on methylation with methyl iodide in absolute ethanol yielded the sulphone. After recrystallisation from dilute ethanol it melted at 94-95°. Kloosterziel and Backer³ report m.p. 93-94°.

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